

Mechanism of Metal Complex catalysed Epoxidation Reactions and a Case Study of Binuclear Complex as Catalyst

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The reactive parts of the enzymes in biological systems are generally associated with a coordinated transition metal ion¹. This has been the reason for growing interest in the study of the metal complexes as models for biochemical systems². Amongst the various reactions of the enzymes, the significant ones are those involving oxygen molecules. On the basis of their functions they have been classified as oxygen carriers (haemoglobin, hemocyanin)^{3,4} oxidases, assisting electron transfer from the substrate and its consequent oxidation (phenol oxidase, ascorbate oxidase)⁵ and oxygenase, assisting combination of oxygen with the substrate⁶.

Oxygenases are of two types. Monooxygenases assist insertion of only one oxygen atom of molecular oxygen to the substrate⁷, whereas dioxygenases catalyse the reaction leading to both the oxygen atoms getting bound with the substrate⁸. The insertion of oxygen occurs through the intermediate binding of molecular oxygen to the metal ion of the enzyme. The reaction between O₂ and a metal ion is a redox process resulting in the formation of a superoxo^{9,10} or peroxo complex¹¹, depending on electron-donating tendency of the metal ion. One-electron donor metal ions react with O₂ in 1 : 1 ratio of O₂ to metal ion to form superoxo complex. Peroxo complexes are expected for metal ions with a preference for two-electron oxidation. The formation of μ -peroxo complexes can also be a consequence of transfer of two electrons to O₂ by two single electron donor metal ions. The intermediate species can be shown as follows :

Mechanism of oxidation reactions involving molecular oxygen as oxidant : A variety of synthetic metalloporphyrins have been used exhaustively as catalysts for hydrocarbon oxidation reactions using various oxygen donors and molecular oxygen as oxidants to mimic the role of naturally occurring monooxygenase Fe^{III} protoporphyrin cytochrome P-450. The remarkable effectiveness of natural metalloporphyrins as oxygenase enzyme is attributed to their planar porphyrin ring with extensive π -conjugation system and a central metal ion with variable valency¹²⁻¹⁵.

In most of the catalytic oxygenation reactions where the molecular oxygen has been used as oxidant, the presence of stoichiometric quantity of reductant is necessary with respect to the quantity of molecular oxygen. This is because the metal ion undergoes two-electron transfer to form peroxo Mⁿ⁺²-O₂⁻² species. The breaking of peroxo bond and formation of Mⁿ⁺²=O takes place only when the second oxygen atom of the peroxo unit is reduced to water by another reducing agent¹⁶,

In natural system NAOH acts as reducing agent. However, in model systems NaBH₄¹⁷⁻²⁰, ascorbate²¹ or colloidal Pt/H₂^{22,23} can be used as reducing agents to convert the second oxygen to water. The metal-oxo formed transfers the oxygen to the substrate, resulting in its oxidation and the regeneration of enzyme.

Metal-oxo intermediates are capable of affecting the following types of oxidative transformation :

More recently a new mechanism has been suggested for Ru^{II} complex catalysed oxidation reactions using molecular oxygen as the source, where both the oxygen atoms are available for oxidation of the substrate and no reducing agent is required for the progress of the reaction.

The formation of two molecules of Ru^{IV}=O takes place via formation of Ru^{III}-μ-peroxy species²⁴.

A similar observation was made by Taquikhan and coworkers in the case of Ru^{III}-EDTA complex as catalyst. In such reactions, both oxygen atoms of the oxygen molecules are used for the substrate oxidation. This is confirmed by the observation that during the oxidation of the olefin, two moles of epoxide are produced for each mole of dioxygen consumed²⁵.

Mechanism of oxidation using mono-oxygen oxidants : The use of reducing agent can also be avoided by using single oxygen donors as oxidants, such as iodobenzene^{26,27}, sodium hypochlorite²⁸, t-butylhydroperoxide²⁹ etc. These oxidants first transfer oxygen to metal complex and then to the

substrate through an oxygen-rebound mechanism proposed by Groves and McClusky³⁰.

Recent studies throw light on the mechanism of oxygen transfer to the olefin. It has been proposed that there is formation of an intermediate species by combination of metal-oxo with alkene, leading to the formation of epoxide. In the formation of the intermediate, there are two possible orientations of approach of alkene to metal-oxo.

- (i) Epoxidation of *cis*-alkene by iron porphyrin results in a stereoselective product. The mechanism has been suggested in which the alkene approaches the oxo iron bond from the top, parallel to the plane of the porphyrin ring (I).

In the epoxidation of alkene by chromylchloride, it was proposed earlier that there is a formation of three-centred cyclic activated complex (II) as a transition state, thus confirming a top approach of the olefin over metal-oxo³¹.

- (ii) An alternate mechanism has been suggested based on the oxidation of olefins at low temperature using chromyl chloride as oxidant. First, the alkene is supposed to get bound to the chromium through one carbon atom resulting in an organometallic intermediate. This is followed by cycloaddition of the other carbon of the olefin with the oxo-chromium bond forming a metallocycle called chromoxetane as transition state³².

In case of ruthenium complexes also, it has been considered that top approach of olefin is

improbable because, with this geometry there will be little non-bonding interaction between the alkene substituent and porphyrin. Hence it was suggested that orientation of alkene to the porphyrin ring is from side (side on approach) giving rise to a metallocycle as transition state³³.

Subsequently, the M–C bond breaks and the carbon gets bound to the oxygen of M–O resulting in the formation of the epoxide. The formation of stereoisomeric mixture of epoxide in some cases can be accounted by considering that there is rotation of C–C bond prior to the cleavage of M–O bond. This results in formation of *trans*-epoxide³⁴.

For the formation of epoxide from metaloxitane M–C and M–O bonds have to break. It was observed that electron-donating substituent on the substrate causes M–C bond cleavage much faster than C–C bond cleavage, resulting in acyclic oxo-metal radical or carbonation. In some cases partial heterocyclic cleavage of the C–C bond in the metallocycle leads to the development of negative charge at the α -carbon of the substituted styrene.

If the metal-oxo is more reactive then oxidative cleavage takes place to give rise to two products. For example, styrene gives benzaldehyde and formaldehyde.

Metalloxetane formation is also supported by recent observation that some olefinic substrates oxidised by cytochrome P-450 cause alkylation of the prosthetic heme group of the enzyme leading to the inhibition of the enzymatic activity. Such olefins are called suicide substrates³⁵. The mechanism can be shown as follows :

After transferring oxygen from metal to the substrate, the metal complexes come back to their original state to continue next catalytic cycle. Alternatively, the metal complex may react with metal-oxo to form a μ -oxo species which are poorly active or unreactive. This leads to termination of catalytic process^{36,37}. Another reason for the inhibition of the catalytic activity is disintegration of the ligand part of the complex catalyst in the presence of the oxidant³⁸.

The formation of μ -oxo dimer is dependent on how easily the metal complex takes up the oxygen from the oxidant and how easily it is transferred to the substrate. The catalytic efficiency of the complex depends on the stability of the intermediate metal-oxo species. When the oxo cation is very stable, its utility as catalyst will be limited. The stable oxo cation will be able to epoxidise electron-rich olefins only³⁹. In the cases where $M^{n+2}=O$ is less stable, an oxide-free radical $M^{n+1}-O^*$ is generated leading to the formation of additional product in the oxidation of olefins besides epoxide⁴⁰.

Role of ligand in the catalytic activity of the complex : The nature of the oxo cation and the redox behaviour of a metal complex is dependent on the nature of the metal ion, its oxocation structure and the nature of the coordinated ligand which controls the electron density on the metal ion centre, and hence the redox behaviour⁴¹.

In case of the Schiff base complex catalysts, it has been shown that redox potential of the metal centre and the product formed in oxygenation reaction, catalysed by such complexes is independent of the position of the substituent, i.e. whether it is on imine carbon or on the aryl ring. It was observed that introduction of electron-withdrawing substituent on the aromatic ring of the catalyst leads to enhancement of the catalytic activity⁴². Recently, it has been shown that the substituent on the aliphatic part of the Schiff base also affects the catalytic activity⁴³. Thus the catalytic reaction can be fine-tuned by making suitable adjustment in the ligand part of the complex catalyst.

In natural metalloporphyrin all the four donor atoms are nitrogen and hence Schiff base ligands with two 'N' and two 'O' coordinating sites are not close models for them. This realisation led to the study of the complexes of Schiff base ligands with four nitrogen coordinating sites as catalysts for oxygenation reaction.

Binuclear complexes as catalysts : Multi-metallic species occupy an important position in modern inorganic chemistry. Investigation of binuclear complexes of transition metals are of contemporary relevance due to their interesting magnetic, catalytic and electron donor properties and as models in bioinorganic chemistry⁴⁴⁻⁴⁸. They belong to two major classes : (i) where the metal centres are close enough to have metal-metal interaction either directly or through a bridge system^{49,50} and (ii) where the metal centres are isolated and have no significant interaction^{51,52}.

Binuclear complexes continue to attract attention largely because of their use as models for iron-oxo proteins and catalysts for oxidation of hydrocarbons.

Mazurek and coworkers reported binuclear copper complexes of a Schiff base obtained by condensation of salicylaldehyde or pyridine 2-carboxaldehyde with 1,3-diaminopropan-2-ol and 1,5-diaminopentan-3-ol⁵³. In these complexes there

are two Schiff base azomethine coordinating sites and endogenous alkoxy bridging group. Binuclear complexes with *endo*-alkoxy and various oxo-bridges have also been studied. Recently Fallon and coworkers have reported binuclear iron complexes of binucleating ligand *N,N'*-bis-salicylideneimine-1,3-diaminopropan-2-ol and *N,N'*-bis-salicylideneimine-1,5-diaminopentan-3-ol⁵⁴.

Binuclear complexes of Mn^{II}, Fe^{III} and Cr^{III} with 1,3-bis[1-pyridine-2-yl]ethylideneamino]propan-2-ol were synthesised in our laboratory and used as catalysts for the epoxidation reaction, in order to study the effect of the presence of *endo*-alkoxy bridge on the formation of active intermediate oxocation, transfer of oxygen to olefin and the formation of terminal μ -oxo product⁵⁵.

In continuation with our study of binuclear Ru^{III} complexes with two distant metal ions centres as catalysts for the epoxidation reactions, the present communication reports the synthesis of alkoxy-bridged binuclear complex of Ru^{III} with 1,3-bis[1-(pyridin-2-yl)ethylideneamino]propan-2-ol and the study of its role as catalysts for epoxidation of alkenes using iodosylbenzene as an oxidant.

Results and Discussion

Structure assignment : The elemental analysis of the complex was found to be in good agreement with the proposed formula [Ru₂(20 PyalPN)Cl₄]-Cl₂.2H₂O (1). The ir spectrum of the complex shows broad band in the region 3 600-3 100 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of water. The spectrum also shows bands in the region 1 620-1 600 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the coordinated azomethine stretching. The $\nu_{\text{Ru-Py}}$ stretching is observed at 285 cm⁻¹ and $\nu_{\text{Ru-Cl}}$ stretching at 320-350 cm⁻¹. The presence of water molecule was confirmed by thermal analysis. Thermogravimetric analysis show that the complex loses water molecules around 110-120° and the loss in weight corresponds to two water molecules.

The ir spectrum of the complex was recorded after heating the complex at 120° for 1 h to remove the water molecules. No broad band is observed at 3 600-3 200 cm⁻¹ showing the absence of water molecules. The band due to ν_{OH} is not seen. This indicates that the hydroxy group gets deprotonated during the formation of the binuclear complex and alkoxy O forms an endogeneous bridge between

two metal centres. The following structure can be suggested for the complex.

The epr spectrum of the complex in the solid state at 298 K, shows anisotropic resonance. The g_{av} value is found to be 2.29 indicating the presence of unpaired electron. There is no hyperfine splitting due to coupling with ruthenium nuclear spin $I = 5/2$ (Ref. 56).

TABLE 1—OXIDATION OF ORGANIC SUBSTRATES WITH PhIO CATALYSED BY RUTHENIUM COMPLEXES (1–3)

Substrate : oxidant : catalyst (mole ratio) = 250 : 50 : 1, Solvent : water-dioxane (1 : 6, v/v), Reaction time = 45 min

Substrate	Product	Yield (%) [*]	
		(1)	(2)
Norbornene	Norbornene oxide	8	9
<i>cis</i> -Cyclooctene	<i>cis</i> -Cyclooctene oxide	10	32
Styrene	Styrene oxide	14	27
	Phenyl acetaldehyde	2	5
<i>trans</i> -4-Octene	<i>trans</i> -4-Octene oxide	4	7
Cyclohexene	Cyclohexene oxide	14	26
	2-Cyclohexen-1-one	2	2
	2-Cyclohexen-1-ol	4	6
Cyclohexanol	Cyclohexanone	65	98

^{*}Yield based on iodosylbenzene charged.

Molar conductance of the complex was determined in DMF solution and it was found to be $89 \Omega^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$ corresponding to 1 : 1 electrolyte. This indicates that one chloride is outside the coordination sphere. Thus it can be inferred that both in the solid form or in DMF solution, four chlorides remain bound with two metal centres at two axial positions and the fifth chloride remains outside the coordination sphere. Since catalytic reactions were carried out in water-dioxane mixture, it was necessary to know the number of free coordination sites available on the metal centre of the complex in this solvent. Hence the molar conductance was measured in water and water-dioxane (1 : 6, v/v) solvents. The molar conduc-

tance in water was found to be $485 \Omega^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$ corresponding to 1 : 5 electrolyte. Similar values were observed in water-dioxane (1 : 6, v/v). This shows that all the chlorides get dissociated in water-dioxane solution.

TABLE 2—OXIDATION OF *cis*-CYCLOOCTENE BY STEPWISE ADDITION OF PhIO USING BINUCLEAR COMPLEX WITH ENDOGENOUS ALKOXO BRIDGE

Alkene = 2.5 mmol, Catalyst = 0.01 mmol, Solvent : water-dioxane (1 : 6, v/v)

PhIO mmol	Yield of epoxide (%)		Turnover number
	based on PhIO	based on alkene	
0.5	21	4.2	11
1.0	22	8.8	22
1.5	21	12.8	32
2.0	21	16.5	41
2.5	20	25.4	51

^{*}Moles of epoxide per mole of catalyst.

Use of the complex as oxidation catalyst : The oxidation reaction was carried out in water-dioxane (1 : 6, v/v) mixture using ruthenium complex as catalyst and iodosylbenzene as an oxidant. The substrates used were norbornene, *cis*-cyclooctene, cyclohexene, styrene, *trans*-4-octene and cyclohexanol.

The analysis of the oxidation product (Table 1) shows that norbornene, *cis*-cyclooctene and *trans*-4-octene gave the corresponding epoxides selectively but styrene gave a mixture of styrene oxide and phenylacetaldehyde. Cyclohexanol was oxidised to cyclohexanone with good yield but the cyclohexane shows very poor activity. The electron-rich olefins, such as norbornene, *cis*-cyclooctene and styrene were found substantially more reactive than acyclic olefin, *trans*-4-octene. In case of cyclohexene, epoxidation is accompanied by a lesser amount of allylic hydroxylation and subsequent formation of ketone.

In the catalytic reaction, iodosylbenzene was completely consumed in 1 h. Further addition of iodosylbenzene to the same reaction mixture showed that the quantity of epoxide was doubled. Addition of iodosylbenzene to the same reaction mixture was continued for five times. It was observed that each time there was the same increase of catalytic activity (Table 2).

Its spectrum of the isolated metal complex shows all the bands of the coordinated ligand after epoxidation reaction, indicating that the complex did not undergo disintegration during the epoxidation reaction.

In the present system PhIO is expected to interact with both the metal centres to generate two $\text{Ru}^{\text{V}}=\text{O}$ sites. In the presence of substrate, both the oxygen atoms are transferred to the substrate to give the corresponding oxidised product. The complex continues to act as a catalyst on repeated addition of the oxidant, showing that the terminating μ -oxo compound is not formed. This indicates that the $\text{Ru}^{\text{V}}=\text{O}$ centres rapidly transfer oxygen to the substrate.

The formation of oxo cation is supported by electronic spectrum and cyclic voltammetric study. The uv-visible spectrum of the metal complex taken in aqueous solution, shows peaks at 211, 322, 846 and 1008 nm. On addition of iodosylbenzene to the aqueous solution of the complex it turns green and shows an intense peak at 381 nm due to formation of $\text{Ru}^{\text{V}}=\text{O}$ intermediate (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Electronic spectra of complex 1 (—) and after addition of PhIO (---) in water-dioxane (1 : 6, v/v).

Cyclic voltammetric study : The cyclic voltammetric study of this binuclear ruthenium complex was carried out in water-dioxane (1 : 6, v/v) under inert atmosphere. The complex shows two reduction potentials, one at +0.14 V and the other at -0.32 V which correspond to $\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}$ and $\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}$ reductions. Similarly, two oxidation potentials are observed at -0.1 V and +0.25 V, which correspond to $\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}$ and $\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}$ oxidation couples respectively.

Iodosylbenzene (3 mmol) was added to a solution of the complex and it was stirred under inert atmosphere for 10 min. Slowly the solution turned green. The cyclic voltammogram of the green solution shows the first reduction potentials at +0.19 V and another at -0.68 V. These reduction

potentials occur at more positive values, indicating the presence of higher oxidation state of the metal ion. They correspond to $\text{Ru}^{\text{V}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}$ and $\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}$ reductions. The oxidation potentials were observed at -0.35 and +0.47 V due to $\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}$ and $\text{Ru}^{\text{IV}}/\text{Ru}^{\text{V}}$ couples respectively. It is thus observed that there is shift in the reduction potential of the intermediate green complex compared to the original complex, indicating the formation of Ru^{V} oxo species (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammogram of complex 1 (—) and after addition of PhIO (---) in water-dioxane (1 : 6, v/v) with NaClO_4 at platinum electrode and scan rate of 50 m s^{-1} .

It is interesting to compare the percentage yield of the oxidation products using present catalyst, with those using binuclear ruthenium(III) Schiff base complex of pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde with *p*-phenylenediamine $[\text{Ru}_2(\text{pyalppd})_2\text{Cl}_4]\text{Cl}_2$ (2)⁵⁷. The results shows that the binuclear complex 2 is better catalyst than binuclear complex 1. It is known that in the oxidation process the olefin gets bound to the $\text{Ru}^{\text{V}}=\text{O}$ forming an intermediate cyclic metalloxetane ring. In the present catalyst, two metal centres are much closer and hence there may be steric hinderance in the simultaneous binding of two metal-oxo to two olefin molecules to form metalloxetane rings. Hence, both centres may not be able to effectively contribute to the catalytic reaction, while in case of complex 2, previously studied, the two Ru^{V} -oxo centres are away from each other and can combine with two olefins

simultaneously, without any hinderance. This results in greater catalytic activity of the latter complex.

Experimental

Synthesis of the complex : To a solution of pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde (2 mmol) in dry ethanol (30 ml) was added a solution of 1,3-diaminopropan-2-ol (1 mmol) in dry ethanol (20 ml) and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 3 min. The Schiff base formed in solution was added dropwise to a solution of ruthenium trichloride (2 mmol) in dry ethanol (50 ml) and the mixture was stirred for 3 h at room temperature under nitrogen atmosphere. The solid separated was filtered washed with dry ethanol and dried under reduced pressure at 100° for 2 h.

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References

- "Bioinorganic Chemistry", ed. R. W. HAY, Ellis Horwood, Halsted, 1984.
- B. MEUNIER, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1986, 578.
- H. REIN, C. JUNG, O. RISTAU and K. RUCKPAUL in "Fundamental Research in Homogeneous Catalysis", ed. A. E. SILOY, 1989, p. 733.
- C. J. WILSHIRE and D. T. SAWYER, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1979, **12**, 105.
- I. TABUSHI and N. KOGA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **101**, 6456.
- "Oxygenases", ed. O. HAYAISHI, Academic, New York, 1962.
- "Hemoglobin : Cooperative and Electronic Properties", ed. M. WEISSBLUTH, Springer Verlag, New York, 1978.
- J. M. RIFKIND in "Inorganic Biochemistry", ed. C. L. EICHARN, Elsevier, New York, 1973, **Vol. II**, p. 832.
- F. A. KLALKER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **9**, 1154.
- H. SUZUKI, K. MIZUTANI, Y. MORO-OKA and T. ITAWA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **101**, 748.
- C. BRAUER, "Hand Book of Preparative Inorganic Chemistry", Academic, New York, 1965, p. 1540.
- "The Porphyrins, Structure and Synthesis", ed. D. DOLPHIN, Academic, New York, 1978, **Vols. I, II**.
- E. D. STEVENS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **103**, 508.
- R. W. JOYNER, J. A. R. VEEN and W. M. H. SACTLER, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans.*, 1982, **78**, 1021.
- F. P. GEUNERICH and T. L. MACDONALD, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1984, **17**, 9.
- M. J. COON and R. E. WHITE in "Metal Ion Activation of Dioxygen", ed. T. C. SPIRO, Wiley, New York, 1980, p. 73.
- H. SAKURI, Y. HETAYA, T. GOROMARU and H. MATSUURA, *J. Mol. Catal.*, 1985, **29**, 153.
- M. SHIMIZU, H. ORITA, T. HAYAKAWA and K. TAKEHIRA, *J. Mol. Catal.*, 1988, **45**, 85.
- Y. ADYAMA, T. KLATANABE, H. ONDA and H. OGOSHI, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1983, **24**, 1183.
- Y. OKAMOTO and S. OKA, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1984, **49**, 1589.
- M. FONTECAVE and D. MANSUY, *Tetrahedron*, 1984, **40**, 4297.
- I. TABUSHI and A. YAZAKI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **103**, 7371.
- I. TABSHI and K. MORIMITSU, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **106**, 6871.
- B. R. JAMES, S. R. MIKKELSEN, T. W. LEUNG, C. M. WILLIAMS and R. WONG, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1984, **85**, 209.
- M. M. TAQUIKHAN and A. P. RAO, *J. Mol. Catal.*, 1987, **39**, 331.
- C. M. CHE, W. L. LEUNG and C. K. POON, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1987, 173.
- M. BRESSAN and A. MORVILLA, *J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1989, **28**, 950.
- J. P. COLLMAN, J. I. BRAUMAN, P. P. HAMPTON, H. TANAKA, D. SCOTT BOHLE and R. T. HEMBRE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **112**, 7980.
- T. C. LAU, C. M. CHE, W. O. LEE and C. K. POON, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1988, 1406.
- J. T. GROVER and C. A. MCCLUSKY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **98**, 859.
- F. FREEMAN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1975, **75**, 439.
- K. B. SHARPLESS, A. Y. TERANISHI and J. E. BACKVALL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **99**, 3120.
- C. HO, W. H. LEUNG and C. M. CHE, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1991, 2933.
- J. T. GROVES, K. H. AHN and R. QUINN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **110**, 4217.

35. B. T. LUKE, J. R. COLLINS, C. H. LQED and A. D. MCLEAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **112**, 8986.
36. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced in Organic Chemistry", 5th. ed., Wiley, New York, 1980.
37. A. C. SYKES, *Chem. Br.*, 1974, 170.
38. G. A. GILBERT, D. S. EGGLESTON, W. R. MURPHY, J. R. D. A. GESELOWITZ, S. W. GERSTON, D. J. HODGEON and T. J. MEYER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **107**, 3855.
39. E. C. SAMSEL, K. SRINIVASAN and J. K. KOCHI, 1985, **107**, 7606.
40. M. J. NAPPA and R. J. MEKINNEY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1988, **27**, 3740.
41. W. M. COLEMAN, R. K. BOGGESS, J. W. HUGES and L. T. TAYLOR, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, **20**, 700.
42. K. SRINIVASAN, S. PERRIER and J. K. KOCHI, *J. Mol. Catal.*, 1986, **36**, 297.
43. F. C. FREDRICK and L. T. TAYLOR, *Polyhedron*, 1986, **5**, 887.
44. S. M. LAMBERT and D. N. HENDRICKSON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, **18**, 2683.
45. S. K. MANDAL, L. K. THOMPSON, K. NAG, J. P. CHARLAND and E. J. GABE, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1987, **65**, 2815.
46. P. LACROIX, O. KAHN, F. THEOBALD, J. LEROY and C. WAKSELEMAN, *Inorg. Chm. Acta*, 1988, **142**, 129.
47. E. I. SOLOMAN in "Copper Proteins", ed. C. SPIRO, Wiley, New York, 1981.
48. K. D. KARLIN and J. ZUBETA, "Copper Coordination Chemistry, Biochemical and Inorganic Perspectives, Adenine", New York, 1983, p. 259.
49. S. K. MANDAL, L. K. THOMPSON, K. NAG, J. P. CHARLAND and E. J. GABE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1987, **26**, 1391.
50. R. C. LONG and D. N. HENDRICKSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **105**, 1513.
51. E. F. HASTY, L. J. WILSON and D. N. HENDRICKSON, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1978, **17**, 1834.
52. P. S. ZACHARIAS and A. RAMACHANDRAIAH, *Polyhedron*, 1985, **4**, 1013.
53. W. MAZUREK, B. J. KENNEDY and K. S. MURRAY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, **21**, 3071.
54. C. D. FALLON, A. MARKIEWICZ, K. S. MURRAY and T. QUACH, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1991, 198.
55. M. J. UPADHYAY, B. M. TRIVEDI, P. K. BHATTACHARYA, P. A. GANESHPURE and S. SATISH, *J. Mol. Catal.*, 1992, **73**, 287.
56. M. M. TAQUIKHAN, D. SRINIVAS, R. J. KURESHY and N. H. KHAN, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, **29**, 2320
57. M. J. UPADHYAY, P. K. BHATTACHARYA, P. A. GANESHPURE and S. SATISH, *J. Mol. Catal.*, 1992, **73**, 277.